

1 **Therapeutic targeting in androgen receptor-positive triple negative breast cancer (AR+ TNBC):**
2 **DUSP3.**

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7 Triple negative breast cancer is defined by combined lack of expression of the hormone receptors *ESR1*,
8 *PGR* and the growth factor receptor *HER2*; thus, endocrine therapy and trastuzumab are generally not
9 considered viable therapies for patients with TNBC (1-5). We recently utilized whole transcriptome
10 technologies to define the full complement of differentially expressed kinases and phosphatases in HER2+
11 breast cancer: in the primary tumor, and in metastasis to the CNS (6-8). Measuring total transcription with
12 RNA-sequencing and microarray in cancer based on quantitative expression of a defined biomarker or the
13 normal tissues from which they are derived enables rational design and development of novel
14 chemotherapies with optimized therapeutic index (9). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies
15 (10, 11) to measure total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with androgen receptor-positive
16 TNBC. We describe a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and differentially expressed in TNBCs that
17 express the androgen receptor, *DUSP3*, as a candidate therapeutic target for the medical management of
18 the primary tumor in AR+ TNBC.
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We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lung, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in primary tumors of the humans with triple negative breast cancers that express the androgen receptor to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the AR+ TNBC transcriptome in humans: a therapeutic target that is differentially expressed based on expression of the androgen receptor, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy in TNBC: DUSP3.

Results

Figure 1: DUSP3 is differentially expressed in the primary tumors of humans with AR+ TNBC.

I. Primary tumors from humans with AR- and AR+ TNBC.

$n=7$ AR- TNBC (human)
 $n=28$ AR+ TNBC (human)

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1845	3.86E-02	0.403	-2.068697	-0.8333709	287.22	DUSP3	1807/19188	90.6

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors in humans with AR- and AR+ TNBC, we discovered differential expression of dual specificity phosphatase 3, encoded by *DUSP3* in TNBC (**Chart 1**). The expression of DUSP3 changed more than 90% of the human AR+ TNBC transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 19,188 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of DUSP3 messenger RNA in androgen receptor-positive triple negative breast cancer (AR+ TNBC) indicating up-regulation of DUSP3 during transformation in AR+ TNBC.

1 II. Primary tumor cells from humans with AR+ and AR- TNBC.

2 *n*=5 AR- TNBC (human)

3 *n*=6 AR+ TNBC (human)

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ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
40519	8.06E-02	-1.9007388	-4.45292	-0.8748794	DUSP3	6624/45015	85.3

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6 Through measurement of total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with AR+ TNBC as
7 compared to AR- TNBC, we validated differential expression of DUSP3 in AR+ TNBC in humans (**Chart
8 2**). The expression of DUSP3 here changed more than 85% of the AR+ TNBC transcriptome when
9 considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 45,015 transcripts ("Rank").
Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of DUSP3 messenger RNA in the primary
tumors of humans with AR+ TNBC, indicating up-regulation of DUSP3 during transformation in AR+
TNBC.

10 Thus, differential and increased expression of DUSP3 defines the tumor transcriptome in human AR+
11 TNBC.

12 **Discussion**

13 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
14 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
15 trastuzumab). Inhibitors of DUSP3, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can immediately be tested for
16 efficacy in patients with AR+ TNBC who have failed previous treatment, with the goal of identifying the
17 most effective first-line chemotherapy regimens for humans with AR+ TNBC, as well as for patients with
18 disease recurrence at the primary site. A multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with
19 chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at
20 anaphase, and target *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is
21 most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (12).

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References

1. Traina, T.A., Miller, K., Yardley, D.A., Eakle, J., Schwartzberg, L.S., O'Shaughnessy, J., Gradishar, W., Schmid, P., Winer, E., Kelly, C. and Nanda, R., 2018. Enzalutamide for the treatment of androgen receptor-expressing triple-negative breast cancer. *Journal of clinical oncology*, 36(9), pp.884-890.
2. Errico, A., 2015. BCL11A—targeting triple-negative breast cancer?. *Nature Reviews Clinical Oncology*, 12(3), pp.127-127.
3. Khaled, W.T., Choon Lee, S., Stingl, J., Chen, X., Raza Ali, H., Rueda, O.M., Hadi, F., Wang, J., Yu, Y., Chin, S.F. and Stratton, M., 2015. BCL11A is a triple-negative breast cancer gene with critical functions in stem and progenitor cells. *Nature communications*, 6(1), p.5987. Khaled, W.T., Choon Lee, S., Stingl, J., Chen, X., Raza Ali, H., Rueda, O.M., Hadi, F., Wang, J., Yu, Y., Chin, S.F. and Stratton, M., 2015.
4. Astvatsaturyan, K., Yue, Y., Walts, A.E. and Bose, S., 2018. Androgen receptor positive triple negative breast cancer: Clinicopathologic, prognostic, and predictive features. *PLoS One*, 13(6), p.e0197827.
5. Giovannelli, P., Di Donato, M., Galasso, G., Di Zazzo, E., Bilancio, A. and Migliaccio, A., 2018. The androgen receptor in breast cancer. *Frontiers in endocrinology*, 9, p.492.
6. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Increased rate of CNS metastasis in patients with HER2+ breast cancer is a result of the intrinsic gene expression program of HER2+ subtype breast cancers, not a consequence of use of the HER2+-targeted drug trastuzumab.
7. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Kinase targeting in HER2+ breast cancer to prevent and treat CNS disease: CDK8.
8. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Catalytic site targeting in HER2+ breast cancer for the treatment of CNS metastasis: PPP1R3D.
9. Muller, P.Y. and Milton, M.N., 2012. The determination and interpretation of the therapeutic index in drug development. *Nature reviews Drug discovery*, 11(10), pp.751-761.
10. GSE244271: Asemota, S., Effah, W., Young, K.L., Holt, J., Cripe, L., Ponnusamy, S., Thiyagarajan, T., Hwang, D.J., He, Y., Mcnamara, K. and Johnson, D., 2023. Identification of a targetable JAK-STAT enriched androgen receptor and androgen receptor splice variant positive triple-negative breast cancer subtype. *Cell reports*, 42(12).
11. GSE38959: Komatsu, M., Yoshimaru, T., Matsuo, T., Kiyotani, K., Miyoshi, Y., Tanahashi, T., Rokutan, K., Yamaguchi, R., Saito, A., Imoto, S. and Miyano, S., 2013. Molecular features of triple negative breast cancer cells by genome-wide gene expression profiling analysis. *International journal of oncology*, 42(2), pp.478-506.
12. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Therapeutic targeting of catalytically available solid tumor vulnerabilities in human cancer.

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Methods

We utilized GSE244271 and GSE38959 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in AR- and AR+ TNBC using RNA-sequencing and microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods.